

LONG-TERM RESPONSE OF VISCOELASTIC COMPOSITE PLATES
ON ELASTIC FOUNDATION

A.M. Vinogradov
Department of Mechanical Engineering
The University of Calgary
Calgary, Alberta, Canada, T2N 1N4

ABSTRACT

The paper deals with the time and temperature-dependent response of viscoelastic composite plates supported by elastic foundation. The mechanical properties of the plate are defined by the constitutive equations of the linear hereditary viscoelasticity coupled with the concept of thermorheologically simple material behaviour. The problem under consideration is solved by means of the quasi-elastic method in conjunction with the finite element analysis. The effectiveness of this approach is illustrated by a numerical example.

KEYWORDS: Laminated Plate Theory; Creep; Viscoelastic; Finite Element Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates have been extensively used in many fields of modern technology, respectively, considerable efforts have been made to examine the response of laminated structural members in a variety of applications. As a significant part of the mechanics of composite materials, the studies of multilayered plates have generated a large number of idealized approaches and computational techniques, see e.g. Ref. (1).

The interaction analysis of multilayered plates supported by continuous foundations is commonly regarded as one of the most involved problems of the laminated plate theory. In this case, one has to deal with a system of two independent components, viz. a composite plate and the supporting base. Accordingly, the respective interaction model must be defined in terms of separate assumptions regarding the responses of both components and the conditions at their interface.

In a number of studies, the interaction problem of multilayered plates is considered in connection with the analysis of floating ice sheets. Specifically, in Ref. (2), a homogeneous ice sheet is idealized as a laminated elastic plate

with the mechanical response of the layers depending on the temperature profile across the ice thickness. Time-dependent deformations of ice sheets due to the creep properties of ice have been studied in Refs. (3) and (4) by introducing into the analysis of non-homogeneous floating plates the assumptions of the linear viscoelastic theory.

This study presents a general analysis of viscoelastic multilayered plates supported by elastic foundation. The response of the plate-base system is defined by an integro-differential equation with respect to the lateral deflection which is treated as a function of the space coordinates, time and temperature. The problem is solved using the quasi-elastic method in conjunction with the finite element analysis. This technique represents a generalization of the approach developed in Ref. (5) in relation to homogeneous viscoelastic plates. The analysis provides a simple numerical solution of a wide range of problems involving various viscoelastic material models and types of the load distribution.

2. INTERACTION MODEL

In this analysis, the deformation of a composite plate is described by the classical multilayered plate theory, see e.g. Ref. (6). Specifically, it is assumed that the plate is composed of a finite number of thin isotropic homogeneous layers bonded together. The deformation of each individual layer is governed by the assumptions of the Kirchhoff's thin plate theory. The lateral displacement is considered to be continuous throughout the thickness of the plate.

The mechanical properties of the plate are described by the constitutive equations of the linear viscoelastic theory coupled with the concept of the thermorheologically simple behaviour of the material, see Ref. (7). It is assumed that each layer has different characteristics in terms of both, the instantaneous elastic and long-term material responses.

The study deals with the time-dependent behaviour of rectangular plates subjected to lateral pressure. It is assumed that the load is applied instantaneously at initial time $t = 0$, and either sustained or gradually increased over the period under consideration. The analysis is concerned with quasi-static loading conditions, respectively, the inertia effects are neglected. The geometry of the plate and the load distribution are defined in terms of the rectangular Cartesian coordinate system shown in Figure 1a.

Based on the foregoing assumptions the strain components of an individual layer, k , ($k = 1,2,3,\dots,n$) are defined as

FIGURE 1. Composite plate supported by continuous foundation:
a) Schematic view; b) Profile of a plate element

$$\varepsilon_{xx}^{(k)} = -z_k \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \quad \varepsilon_{yy}^{(k)} = -z_k \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2}, \quad \varepsilon_{xy}^{(k)} = -2z_k \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (1)$$

where $w = w(x,y,t)$ denotes the lateral deflection.

The linear viscoelastic constitutive equations describing the properties of each layer are of the same form as the Hooke's law in which the elastic constants E_k and ν_k are replaced by the respective integral operators E_k^* and ν_k^* . The operator E_k^* is defined by the uniaxial stress-strain relation

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{1}{E_k^*} \left\{ \sigma_k(t) \right\} = \frac{\sigma_k(t)}{E_k} + \frac{1}{E_k} \int_0^t \Gamma_k(\theta - \theta') \sigma_k(\theta') d\tau \quad (2)$$

in which E_k is the instantaneous elastic modulus, and $\Gamma_k(\theta - \theta')$ represents the creep properties of the k -th layer.

In accordance with the concept of thermorheologically simple materials the parameter θ in Eq. (2) denotes the so-called reduced time which is related to the actual time, t , by the equation

$$\theta(t) \equiv \int_0^t d\tau / a_T \quad (3)$$

where a_T is the temperature shift factor

$$a_T = a_T [T(t)] \quad (4)$$

The operator ν_k^* represents, in general, the dilatational creep properties of the material. In practice, however, it is often assumed that

$$\nu_k^* = \text{const.} = \nu_k \quad (5)$$

where ν_k denotes the instantaneous Poisson's ratio of the k -th layer.

By combining the kinematic relations, the viscoelastic constitutive law and the equations of equilibrium of a plate element one arrives at the governing integro-differential equation

$$D^* \left\{ \nabla^4 w(x,y,\theta) \right\} = p(x,y,t) - q(x,y,t) \quad (6)$$

where ∇^4 signifies two successive applications of the Laplace operator, p and q represent, respectively, the external load and the contact pressure at the interface, as shown in Figure 1b, and D^* denotes an operator function of E_k^* ($k = 1,2,3,\dots,n$) which can be regarded as the viscoelastic prototype of the transformed flexural rigidity of a geometrically similar elastic plate, see Ref. (6).

Thus,

$$D^* = \frac{A^* C^* - B^{*2}}{A^*} \quad (7)$$

where

$$A^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{E_k^* (z_k - z_{k-1})}{1 - \nu_k^2}; \quad B^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{E_k^* (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)}{1 - \nu_k^2} \frac{1}{2}; \quad (8)$$

$$C^* = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{E_k^* (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3)}{1 - \nu_k^2} \frac{1}{3}$$

By introducing Eqs. (8) into Eq. (7) and applying the algebra rules for the convolution integral operators, see Ref. (8), one can obtain the equation for D^* explicitly provided that the kernels of the operators E_k^* ($k = 1,2,3,\dots,n$) are specified.

Note that Eq. (6) contains two unknowns, w and q . In order to establish an additional relation between these functions one has to define the model of the base and formulate the interface conditions. For example, if the base is

represented by the Winkler model and the continuity condition for w at the interface is fulfilled, Eq. (6) assumes the form

$$D^* \left\{ \nabla^4 w(x,y,\theta) \right\} + \gamma w(x,y,\theta) = p(x,y,t) \quad (9)$$

where γ denotes the Winkler coefficient.

The solution of the governing Eq. (6) must satisfy certain boundary and initial conditions. In this analysis, it is assumed that the boundary conditions are stationary in time, and the initial condition reflects the assumption that the response of the plate at the time of the load application is instantaneously elastic.

3. SOLUTION TECHNIQUE

The problem defined by Eq. (6) together with the boundary and initial conditions is solved by means of a two-step solution technique. Firstly, the viscoelastic analysis is reduced to a sequence of identical elastic problems using the concept of the quasi-elastic approximation. As a second step, the elastic solutions are obtained by means of the finite element method.

The quasi-elastic procedure suggested in Ref. (9) for the linear viscoelastic stress analysis is based on the observation that under static and quasi-static loading conditions involving relatively slow deformation rates the viscoelastic response can be approximately replaced by the behaviour of a fictitious elastic material with time-dependent mechanical characteristics. The latter are defined in terms of the relaxation functions or creep compliances of the actual viscoelastic material.

In relation to Eq. (6) the quasi-elastic method entails the replacement of the integral operator $D^* \left\{ \nabla^4 w(x,y,\theta) \right\}$ by the product $[D^* \{1\}] \cdot w(x,y,\theta)$ where $D^* \{1\}$ is a function of time. The latter is obtained from Eqs. (7) and (8) in which the integral operators E_k^* ($k = 1,2,3,\dots,n$) are replaced by the functions

$$\bar{E}_k(t) = \frac{E_k}{1 + \psi_k(t)}, \quad k = 1,2,3,\dots,n \quad (10)$$

where ψ denotes the creep function of the k -th layer of the plate

$$\psi_k = \int_0^t \Gamma_k(\theta - \theta') d\tau, \quad k = 1,2,3,\dots,n \quad (11)$$

As a result of the quasi-elastic procedure, the viscoelastic analysis is reduced to a sequence of identical elastic problems in which the layers of the plate are represented by their individual elastic characteristics that depend

parametrically on time.

According to Eqs. (10) and (11), at $t = 0$, $\bar{E}_k(0) = E_k$ which indicates that at the time of the load application the responses of the actual viscoelastic plate and its elastic prototype precisely coincide. Hence, the quasi-elastic approximate solution satisfies exactly the initial condition of the original viscoelastic problem.

At the second step, the analysis of the elastic composite plate can be performed using the methods of the elastic laminated plate theory. In this regard, one notes that the elastic problem can be effectively treated by means of the finite element method, see, e.g. Refs. (10) and (11). Particularly, in Ref. (5), a hybrid finite element model is used to solve the interaction problem of viscoelastic homogeneous plates. This model is composed of isotropic plate elements with four nodes, straight edges and twelve nodal d.o.f.'s. The same approach can be readily modified for the multilayered plate analysis by introducing a variable element stiffness matrix representing the individual properties of the layers.

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

As an illustration of the solution technique described in the foregoing section, consider the deformation of a composite laminated plate used in Ref. (4) as a model of a floating ice platform. The formulation of the problem is based on the following assumptions. A rectangular composite plate with the surface area 230 m x 180 m and thickness $h = 6$ m is subjected to uniform lateral pressure $p = 0.75 \times 10^4 \text{ N/m}^2$ distributed over the area 66 m x 9 m at the centre. The plate is composed of four separate layers of thickness $h_k = 1.5$ m ($k = 1,2,3,4$). The plate is hinge supported along its boundaries and rests on the Winkler foundation with the elastic coefficient $\gamma = 9.8 \times 10^3 \text{ N/m}^3$.

The material properties of the plate are described by the Maxwell-Kelvin model shown in Figure 2. It is assumed that each layer of the plate is characterized by its individual creep function

$$\psi_k = \frac{E'}{E''} \left[1 - \exp(-\mu\theta_k) \right] + \frac{E'}{E''} \cdot \frac{\eta''}{\eta'} (\mu\theta_k), \quad k = 1,2,3,4 \quad (12)$$

in which $\mu = E''/\eta''$, and θ_k depends on the position of the layer in terms of the coordinate z_k .

Furthermore, the layers of the plate are assumed to have different instantaneous elastic characteristics. The dependence of the respective Young's moduli E_k on z_k is considered in the form

FIGURE 2. Normalized central deflection of the composite plate

$$E_k = E_1 \left(1 - 0.2 \frac{z_{k-1}^2}{h^2} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, 3, 4 \quad (13)$$

where $E_1 = 690$ MPa and $z_0 = 0$. The Poisson's ratio is assumed to be constant across the thickness of the plate, $\nu = 0.33$.

The results of this analysis are presented in Figures 2 and 3. These diagrams demonstrate a monotonic increase of the lateral deflection, w , with respect to non-dimensional time, μt . The numerical values of w are normalized with respect to the parameter

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{pA} \cdot \left[\frac{\gamma E_1 h^3}{12(1-\nu^2)} \right]^{1/2} \quad (14)$$

where A denotes the loading area.

Note that a similar normalizing parameter is used in Ref. (3) with the objective to exclude the effects of the plate geometry and the size of the loading region. It is of interest that the results obtained from this study and those reported in Ref. (3) are comparable in terms of the general patterns of the time-dependent response of the viscoelastic composite plate and the range of computed values of the lateral deflection.

FIGURE 3. Time-dependent deflection profiles of the composite plate

It is important to indicate that the solution technique proposed in this study does not imply that, in general, the individual properties of the composite plate layers must be defined by the same constitutive model as it is assumed in the numerical example. Indeed, the layers of the plate can be represented by different creep functions and different instantaneous elastic characteristics.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study presents a consistent theoretical approach to the analysis of multilayered plates supported by elastic foundation. The formulation of the problem is based on the assumptions of the linear viscoelastic theory and the concept of thermorheologically simple material behaviour. The problem is defined by an integro-differential equation with respect to the lateral deflection which satisfies certain boundary and initial conditions. The problem is solved by means of the quasi-elastic method combined with the finite element analysis. This approach affords a general solution with no restrictive assumptions regarding the distribution of the load, boundary conditions and the material models of the individual layers of the composite plate.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The financial support of this work by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada in the form of an operating research grant is gratefully acknowledged.

7. REFERENCES

1. C.-Y. Chia, *AMR*, 41 (12), 439 (1988).
2. A.P.S. Selvadurai, *IAHR Ice Symposium*, 123 (1984).
3. D. Hui, *J. Strain Analysis*, 21 (3), 135 (1986).
4. A.M. Vinogradov in T.K.S. Murthy, et.al., eds., *Ice Technology, Proceedings of the 1st International Conference*, Springer-Verlag, 1986, p. 397.
5. A.M. Vinogradov and M.J. Loikkanen, in T. Kawai, ed., *Finite Element Flow Analysis, Proceedings of the 4th International Symposium on Finite Element Methods*, University of Tokyo Press, 1982, p. 371.
6. R. Szilard, *Theory and Analysis of Plates: Classical and Numerical Methods*, Prentice Hall, 1974, p. 390.
7. R.M. Christensen, *Theory of Viscoelasticity: An Introduction*, Academic Press, N.Y., 1971, pp. 3, 96.
8. Yu. N. Rabotnov, *Creep Problems in Structural Members*, North-Holland Publishing Co., N.Y., 1969, p. 110.
9. R.A. Schapery, *J. Franklin Inst.*, 279 (4), 268 (1965).
10. M. Epstein and H.P. Huttelmaier, *Computers and Structures*, 16 (5), 645 (1983).
11. O.J. Svec, *J. Engg. Mech. Division*, 102 (EM3), 461 (1976).